

Effect of plyometric, olympic lift and their combination on the performance of shot put

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Abstract. The purpose of the present study was to determine effect of plyometric, olympic lift and their combination on the performance of shot put. The subjects were 60 male shot putters of 17 to 22 years of age group from Government Arts and Sports collage stadium, Jalandhar (Punjab). The subjects were randomly selected and were assigned to the three experimental groups (Plyometric, Olympic lift and combined Plyometric and Olympic lift) and one control group with 20 subjects in each group. The training was given for a period of 6 weeks. The three experimental groups were trained thrice a week, while the control group continued with their daily routine work. The performances of shot put were selected for collecting data. The pre and post test were conducted to collect the data. After the collection of data, the t- test was used to identify any significant differences between the groups. An analysis of co-variance was also used to determine significant differences for the shot put performance. The LSD Post hoc test was used to identify significant differences between the training programs. The level of significance was 0.05. The finding have shown the significant value of F- ratio's for the performance in shot put for all the experimental groups i.e. plyometric, Olympic lift and combined (Plyometric and Olympic lift), training programs as compared with the control group. The combined training program proved better than the other methods.

Key words: *plyometric training, olympic lifting, shot put.*

Introduction

Sport is as old as human society and it has achieved a universal following in the modern times. It has enjoyed a popularity, which outstrips any other form of social activity. It has become an integral part of educational process. Today the sports persons are trained scientifically with the latest training methods and sophisticated instruments for higher performance improvement in different sphere of sports. Contemporary sports science has enable the sports person to develop physically for competition and as a result the records are being broken at a great speed (1).

Over the past decade, plyometric training has gained tremendous popularity as a means of improving explosive strength. Plyometric is the term now applied to exercises that have their roots in Europe where they were first known simply as jump training. Origin of the term plyometric is derived from word pleythyein which means to increase or from the Greek words *plyo* and *metric* which means *more* and *measures* (2).

Olympic lifting contest two lifts: the snatch and the clean and jerk. Over the years this form of training has been employed extensively to improve many power oriented movements in a variety of sports.

There are many variations on the theme of power training. Some of these training principles include plyometrics, assisted and resisted training and speed and acceleration drills. A popular method used to increase athletic power is Olympic lifting (ie power cleans, push presses, snatches, jump jerks and their variations) conducted in the weight room. Power cleans; push presses, snatches, etc. are used by strength and conditioning coaches in an attempt to increase the athletes' general power ability, and is then assumed to transfer over to sporting activity.

From the arguments presented so far; fundamentally, power is governed by neurological processes; neurological processes are governed by the motor cortex;